

Near-optimal feedback control for postprandial glucose regulation in type 1 diabetes

R. Sanz^a, P. García^a, S. Romero-Vivó^{b,c}, J.L. Díez^{a,c}, J. Bondia^{a,c}

^a*Instituto de Automática e Informática Industrial, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 València, Spain*

^b*Instituto de Matemática Multidisciplinar, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 València, Spain*

^c*Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Diabetes y Enfermedades Metabólicas Asociadas (CIBERDEM), 28029 Madrid, Spain*

Abstract

This paper is focused on feedback control of postprandial glucose levels for patients with type 1 Diabetes Mellitus. There are two important limitations that make this a challenging problem. First, the slow subcutaneous insulin pharmacokinetics that introduces a significant lag into the control loop. Second, the positivity constraint on the control action, meaning that it is not possible to remove insulin from the body. In this paper, both issues are explicitly considered in the design process using the internal model control framework, to derive a near-optimal feedback controller. Optimality is understood here as minimizing the blood glucose peak after a meal intake and, at the same time, preventing glucose values below a prescribed threshold. It is shown how the proposed controller approaches the optimal closed-loop performance as a limit case. The theoretical results are supported by a numerical example and the feasibility of the overall strategy under uncertainties is illustrated using an extended version UVa/Padova metabolic simulator.

Keywords: artificial pancreas, positive systems, disturbance attenuation, internal model control

Email addresses: risanda@upv.es (R. Sanz), pggil@isa.upv.es (P. García), sromero@mat.upv.es (S. Romero-Vivó), jldiez@isa.upv.es (J.L. Díez), jbondia@isa.upv.es (J. Bondia)

1. Introduction

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM) is a metabolic disorder that results in the incapability of the pancreas to secrete insulin, a hormone responsible for lowering blood glucose concentration. As a result, a T1DM patient typically suffers from high plasma glucose concentration (hyperglycemia) over prolonged periods of time, leading to serious cardiovascular complications in the long term [1]. Standard T1DM treatment is based on patients self-control, requiring the administration of insulin analogs via multiple daily injections or by means of an insulin pump with manual dosing adjustments (open-loop therapy). Changes in the patient insulin sensitivity or inaccurate insulin dosing may lead to excessively low blood glucose levels (hypoglycemia), which could be life-threatening if untreated long enough. An artificial pancreas (AP) is a system composed of three elements: i.) a continuous glucose monitoring device (CGM) [2]; ii.) an insulin infusion pump; and iii.) a control algorithm, which automatically computes the insulin dosing in order to keep blood glucose levels within the normal range (closed-loop therapy) [3]. In the review [4], eighteen APs were identified in different phases of study. Although the improvement of an AP in glucose regulation compared to open-loop therapy is widely acknowledged [5, 6, 7, 8], current commercially available APs still have limitations [9].

The problem of postprandial unannounced control, that is, after a meal intake and without the patient intervention, is especially challenging [10]. On the one hand, there is a significant lag from the time subcutaneous insulin is delivered until plasma glucose concentration is actually lowered. On the other hand, the control action is constrained to be positive, that is, removing insulin from the body is not possible. These two facts pose difficulties for the design of closed-loop controllers. In order to achieve the desired performance, current APs still need from the patient intervention to “announce” the meal, which serves as a feedforward action, triggering a prandial insulin bolus as in open-loop therapy. However, this is a significant burden for patients, who have to estimate the carbohydrate (CHO) content of their meal as in open-loop therapy. Postprandial glucose regulation is an active topic of research, for which a wide variety of feedback control strategies have been investigated. Conventional PID-based techniques are often combined with ad-hoc structures to avoid insulin over-delivery and provide additional safety [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Model predictive controllers have been employed [16, 17, 18, 19], using a switching cost function to deal with postprandial scenarios [20]. Other switching strategies within the context of H_∞ control have been also reported [21]. This challenging problem has been also approached by means of meal detection algorithms, which are often used to deliver appropriate insulin boluses [22, 23, 24, 25]. All the aforementioned strategies have in common the use of heuristics or ad-hoc structures to overcome the challenges of this particular control application.

In the context of postprandial control, better performance is understood as reducing the blood glucose peak while ensuring that the minimum thereafter does not fall below a prescribed threshold. It was shown in [26] that the optimal open-loop control policy consists in delivering an insulin bolus before mealtime, that is, an impulsive feedforward control action. However, this policy requires future knowledge of the disturbance, which means it cannot be generated by feedback. Furthermore, it relies on the patient intervention, who has to estimate the carbohydrate content of the meal and to compute the appropriate insulin dose. In this work, the relationship between open-loop and closed-loop optimality is first investigated. A feedback controller is derived, which does not need any meal information, neither carbohydrate content nor intake time, releasing the patient from that burden. The positivity of the control signal is handled within the internal model control (IMC) framework. It is then proved that optimal closed-loop performance is approached as a limit case. Simulation results illustrate that the proposed controller has the following features: near-optimal nominal closed-loop performance, systematic model-based design with a single patient-tailored clinical-based tuning parameter and reduced computational burden, which depart from existing literature.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. The problem is formally stated in Section 2, where the proposed strategy is introduced and some of the controller properties are derived. Section 3 is devoted to the tuning of the controller and its relationship with the optimal control policy. Finally, in Section 4, the theoretical results are supported with a numerical example and the feasibility of this approach is illustrated with a simulation using an extended version of the UVa/Padova simulator.

2. Proposed control strategy

The control problem is formally stated in this section and an IMC-based controller is derived to guarantee closed-loop stability and positivity of the control action.

2.1. Problem statement

The postprandial glucose levels of a T1DM patient can be modeled by [27]

$$y(s) = G_d(s)e^{-l_d s}d(s) - G_u(s)e^{-l_u s}u(s), \quad (1)$$

where

$$G_d(s) = \frac{K_d}{\prod_{i=1}^{r_d}(\tau_{d_i} s + 1)} \quad \text{and} \quad G_u(s) = \frac{K_u}{\prod_{i=1}^{r_u}(\tau_{u_i} s + 1)}$$

are positive real transfer functions with gains $K_d, K_u > 0$ and relative degrees $r_d, r_u \in \mathbb{Z}_+$; y is the blood glucose deviation with respect its basal value y_b , achieved with a basal insulin infusion rate $u_b > 0$; u is

Figure 1: Proposed control structure

the incremental insulin infusion rate with respect to u_b ; and d is an impulse signal

$$d(t) = M\delta(t - t_0), \quad \forall t \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

modeling an ideal meal intake with CHO content $M > 0$, delivered at time $t_0 \geq 0$, being $\delta(t)$ the Dirac delta function.

Assumption 1. *The models $G_d(s)$, $G_u(s)$ and their corresponding delays $l_d, l_u \geq 0$, are known*

Assumption 2. *The control input is constrained to be positive, that is, $u(t) \geq 0, \forall t \geq 0$*

The structure of the plant and the disturbance is motivated by the multiple-compartment models often used in the T1DM literature. Some works use the same number of compartments for the insulin and meal dynamics ($r_u = r_d$) [28], while others use higher-order models for the insulin subsystem ($r_u > r_d$) [29, 30]. The meal disturbance structure (2) implies that the gut absorption rate is represented by the impulse response of a compartmental model, which is standard in the literature [17]. Assumption 1 is needed to show the relationship with the optimal control policy in the nominal case. However, the feasibility of this approach under model uncertainties is illustrated through simulations in Section 4.3. Assumption 2 is reasonable in the context of T1DM [26], although this assumption can be relaxed as explained in Remark 7.

2.2. Stability and positivity constraint

Let us consider the IMC-based control loop represented in Fig. 1a, with a strictly-proper stable filter $Q(s)$ to be designed. Rearranging this block diagram into the conventional control loop depicted in Fig. 1b, leads to the so-called Youla parameterization

$$u(s) = -K(s)y(s) = \frac{Q(s)}{1 - Q(s)G_u(s)e^{-l_us}}y(s), \quad (3)$$

It is well known that any stabilizing controller $K(s)$ for the plant $G_u(s)e^{-l_us}$ can be written in the form of (3). One of the benefits of this parameterization is that the relevant closed-loop transfer functions are affine with respect to $Q(s)$ [31]. In particular, the transfer function from the disturbance to the control signal, which is given by

$$\frac{u(s)}{d(s)} = Q(s)G_d(s)e^{-l_ds}, \quad (4)$$

will be used in the subsequent developments.

Theorem 1. *Under Assumptions 1-2, the closed-loop system composed of the plant (1) driven by the disturbance (2) and the controller (3) with $Q(s)$ computed by*

$$Q(s) = \frac{k}{K_d} \frac{\prod_{i=1}^{r_d} (\tau_{d_i}s + 1)}{(\alpha s + 1)^r} \quad (5)$$

is internally stable for any $r \geq r_d$ and $\alpha, k > 0$. Furthermore, the analytic expression of the closed-loop control signal is given by

$$u(t, \alpha, r, k) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < \tau_0 \\ \frac{kM}{\alpha^r (r-1)!} (t - \tau_0)^{r-1} e^{-\frac{t-\tau_0}{\alpha}}, & t \geq \tau_0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $\tau_0 = t_0 + l_d$, which satisfies

$$B \triangleq \int_{\tau_0}^{\infty} u(t, \alpha, r, k) dt = kM \quad (7)$$

for any $\alpha, k > 0$ and $r \geq 1$.

Proof. Using (2) and (5) into (4) yields

$$u(s) = \frac{kM}{(\alpha s + 1)^r} e^{-\tau_0 s}, \quad (8)$$

and taking the inverse Laplace transform of (8) leads to (6). Note that the condition $r \geq r_d$ implies that (5) is realizable. Furthermore, the open-loop plant, $G(s)e^{-l_us}$, is stable, and so is $Q(s)$ in (5) for any

$r \geq r_d$ and $\alpha, k > 0$, which guarantees the internal closed-loop stability [31]. The property (7) can be derived from

$$\int_{\tau_0}^T u(t, \alpha, r, k) dt = \frac{kM}{(r-1)!} \gamma\left(r, \frac{T-\tau_0}{\alpha}\right) \quad (9)$$

which follows by plugging (6) into the integral and performing the change of variable $s = (t - \tau_0)/\alpha$, being $\gamma(r, x) = \int_0^x s^{r-1} e^{-s} ds$ the lower incomplete gamma function. It is verified that $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(r, x) = \Gamma(r) = (r-1)!$, where $\Gamma(r)$ is the complete gamma function, and thus (7) follows by letting $T \rightarrow \infty$ in (9). \square

Remark 1 (Clinical tuning). *From (7), the total insulin delivered during the postprandial period, B , is proportional to the meal size M . However, the proposed controller does not need information about the meal size nor the intake time to be implemented. The parameter k is clearly related to the $I2C$ (insulin-to-carbohydrate ratio), which is an important clinical parameter for a diabetic patient, as it is used to compute the prandial insulin bolus. From (7), one has that $I2C = M/B = 1/k$ and this fact can be actually used as a rule of thumb for tuning, as illustrated below in Section 4.3.*

Remark 2 (DOB-equivalency). *The proposed controller, composed of (3) and (5), can be rewritten in the following form*

$$\hat{d}(s) = F(s)G_d(s)^{-1}[y(s) + G_u(s)e^{-l_u s}u(s)] \quad (10)$$

$$u(s) = k\hat{d}(s) \quad (11)$$

with $F(s) = 1/(\alpha s + 1)^r$. To prove this, simply note that (3) can be obtained by plugging (10) into (11), solving for $u(s)$ and using that $Q(s)$ in (5) can be written as $Q(s) = kF(s)G_d(s)^{-1}$. In the form (10)-(11), it is clear that the proposed controller estimates a delayed meal disturbance $\bar{d}(t) \triangleq e^{-l_d s}d(t)$ and delivers insulin proportionally. This is a so-called disturbance observer (DOB)-based controller [32]. DOBs have been previously employed in the context of artificial pancreas. However, they are often used to derive meal detection and bolusing algorithms [24, 25, 33], or they need to be combined with other structures to avoid insulin over-delivery when used in a continuous feedback control loop [34, 35].

3. Optimality analysis

In this section, some results on optimal postprandial control are first revisited. The tuning of the proposed strategy is then investigated and it is proved that the optimal closed-loop policy is obtained as a limit case.

3.1. Optimal control problem

As explained in the Introduction, better performance in the context of postprandial control is achieved by reducing the glucose peak while keeping the subsequent glucose levels above a prescribed threshold, which will be denoted by y^{min} . In order to state this formally, let us define $h_u(t), h_d(t) \geq 0, \forall t \geq 0$; $h_u(t), h_d(t) = 0, \forall t < 0$, as the unit impulse responses associated to $G_u(s)$ and $G_d(s)$, respectively, that is, $h_u(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{G_u(s)\}(t)$, $h_d(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{G_d(s)\}(t)$. Also, similar to [26], let us consider the set of control input signals

$$\mathcal{U} = \{u(t) : u(t) = 0, \forall t < \tau_u; u(t) \geq 0, \forall t \geq \tau_u\} \quad (12)$$

with a parameter $\tau_u \in \mathbb{R}$ (see Remarks 3 and 4 for further explanation); and the following assumption:

Assumption 3. *There exist \bar{t}, \underline{t} , defined by $y(\bar{t}) = \max_t y(t)$ and $y(\underline{t}) = \min_t y(t)$, such that $\tau_u + l_u < \bar{t} < \underline{t}$*

This is a reasonable assumption in diabetes control, given the slow effect of current insulin analogs compared to the meal impact in blood glucose levels, which indicates that the minimum of the response occurs after the maximum peak is reached. Moreover, it also implies that the peak cannot occur before the control input has had effect on the output (otherwise, delivering insulin would be pointless). Using (1)-(2), the output of the system can be expressed in the time-domain as

$$y(t) = Mh_d(t - \tau_0) - (h_u * u)(t - l_u) \quad (13)$$

Then, in the context of this work, the optimal control problem can be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} u^*(t) = \arg \min_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \quad & \max_t y(t) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \text{Equation (13)} \quad \text{and} \quad \min_t y(t) \geq y^{min} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Considering the results in [26], the optimal solution to (14) under Assumption 3 can be written as

$$u^*(t) = B^*(\tau_u)\delta(t - \tau_u), \quad (15)$$

that is, an insulin bolus delivered at time τ_u , where the bolus size B^* must be appropriately selected so that the prescribed value y^{min} is reached. A model-based expression for $B^*(\tau_u)$ is derived in the following lemma, which will be used later in Corollary 1.

Lemma 1. *The optimally-sized bolus in (15) for (1)-(2) can be computed by*

$$B^*(\tau_u) = \min_{t \geq \min\{\tau_0, l_u + \tau_u\}} \left(\frac{h_d(t - \tau_0) - y^{\min}/M}{h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u)} \right) M \quad (16)$$

Proof. See Appendix A. □

Remark 3 (Open-loop optimality). *In open-loop control, the time τ_u in (12) can be arbitrarily selected. It was shown in [26] that the optimal value, τ_u^* , is the smallest possible so that Assumption 3 remains valid. Note that the optimal open-loop policy, $B^*(\tau_u^*)$, requires future knowledge of the disturbance to be implemented, as illustrated in Fig. 3.*

Remark 4 (Closed-loop optimality). *The optimal open-loop policy cannot be generated by feedback because the output is not even affected by the disturbance until $\tau_0 = t_0 + l_d$. In other words, τ_u in (12) is lower bounded by τ_0 . Since the optimal τ_u is the smallest possible, that leads to the conclusion that the best performance achievable by feedback is obtained by applying the control input $B^*(\tau_0)$.*

3.2. Sub-optimal closed-loop control

Next, it will be shown that, as a limit case, the proposed controller approaches the best control policy achievable by feedback, $B^*(\tau_0)$. To that end, the tuning of the controller is investigated. In what follows, let

$$u_1(t) \triangleq u(t, \alpha_1, r_1, k_1) \quad \text{and} \quad u_2(t) \triangleq u(t, \alpha_2, r_2, k_2)$$

denote two controllers as defined by (6), with different sets of tuning parameters. Also, let $y_1(t)$ and $y_2(t)$ be the outputs resulting from applying the control laws $u_1(t)$ and $u_2(t)$ to the system (1), respectively, when the latter is driven by (2). Next, some definitions and a technical lemma are stated before introducing the main result of this section.

Definition 1. *Given the system (1) driven by the disturbance (2), a controller $u_2(t)$ leading to the output $y_2(t)$ is better than a controller $u_1(t)$ leading to the output $y_1(t)$ if $\max_t y_2(t) < \max_t y_1(t)$ and $\min_t y_2(t) \geq y^{\min}$, where $y^{\min} < 0$ is a design requirement.*

Definition 2. *Given the system (1) driven by the disturbance (2), let us define $k^\dagger = k^\dagger(\alpha, r) > 0$ as the value that achieves $\min_t y(t) = y^{\min}$, where $y(t)$ is the output resulting from applying $u(t, \alpha, r, k^\dagger)$ as defined in (6).*

Lemma 2. *The value of $k^\dagger(\alpha, r)$ in Definition 2 can be computed by*

$$k^\dagger(\alpha, r) = \min_{t > \tau_0} \frac{h_d(t - \tau_0) - y^{\min}/M}{(h_u * f)(t - l_u - \tau_0)} \quad (17)$$

with $f(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{(\alpha s + 1)^{-r}\}(t)$.

Proof. See Appendix B. □

Lemma 3. *Let $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2$ and $1 \leq r_1 \leq r_2$; then there exist $\kappa > 0$ and $\tau > \tau_0$ such that:*

a.) *If $r_1 = r_2$ and $k_2 \geq \kappa$:*

$$u_2(t) - u_1(t) > 0, \quad \forall t > \tau_0 \quad (18)$$

b.) *Otherwise:*

$$u_2(t) - u_1(t) < 0, \quad \forall t \in (\tau_0, \tau) \quad (19)$$

$$u_2(t) - u_1(t) > 0, \quad \forall t > \tau \quad (20)$$

Proof. See Appendix C. □

Theorem 2. *Let $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2$, $1 \leq r_1 \leq r_2$ and $k_1 = k^\dagger(\alpha_1, r_1)$; then $u_2(t)$ cannot be better than $u_1(t)$*

Proof. Recall that $y_1(t)$ and $y_2(t)$ are the outputs resulting from applying the control laws $u_1(t)$ and $u_2(t)$, respectively. Also, let us define $\bar{t}_1, \underline{t}_1$ such that $y_1(\bar{t}_1) = \max_t y_1(t)$ and $y_1(\underline{t}_1) = \min_t y_1(t)$, which exist by Assumption 3. The proof will be shown by contradiction. Let us make the hypothesis that there exists a control $u_2(t)$ better than $u_1(t)$. Then, by Definition 1, one has that $\max_t y_2(t) < \max_t y_1(t) = y_1(\bar{t}_1)$, and taking into account that $y_2(\bar{t}_1) \leq \max_t y_2(t)$, it is clear that

$$\Delta y(\bar{t}_1) \triangleq y_1(\bar{t}_1) - y_2(\bar{t}_1) > 0 \quad (21)$$

must hold for the hypothesis to be true. Definition 1 implies also $\min_t y_2(t) \geq y^{min} = \min_t y_1(t)$, where the last equality holds by Definition 2, provided that $k_1 = k^\dagger(\alpha_1, r_1)$; and thus

$$\Delta y(\underline{t}_1) \triangleq y_1(\underline{t}_1) - y_2(\underline{t}_1) \leq 0 \quad (22)$$

must hold by similar arguments as above. It will be shown next that, under the conditions stated in this theorem, (21)-(22) cannot be satisfied and thus the hypothesis is false. Both outputs $y_1(t)$ and $y_2(t)$ at any time $t \geq 0$ can be expressed as

$$y_j(t) = M h_d(t - \tau_0) - \int_0^t h_u(t - \theta - l_u) u_j(\theta) d\theta \quad (23)$$

for $j = \{1, 2\}$. Notice that, from (6), both u_1, u_2 belong to \mathcal{U} in (12) with $\tau_u = \tau_0$ and thus $\tau_0 + l_u < \bar{t}_1 < \underline{t}_1$

holds by Assumption 3. Then, evaluating (23) at $\underline{t}_1, \bar{t}_1$ for $j = \{1, 2\}$ and subtracting leads to the following expressions

$$\Delta y(\bar{t}_1) = \int_{\tau_0}^{\bar{t}_1 - l_u} h_u(\bar{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta y(\underline{t}_1) = \int_{\tau_0}^{\underline{t}_1 - l_u} h_u(\underline{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \quad (25)$$

where the lower and upper limits of the integrals have been truncated using that $u_j(t) = 0, \forall t < \tau_0$ and $h_u(t) = 0, \forall t < 0$. Let us consider first the case a.) in Lemma 3. Then from (18) and (25), it follows that $\Delta y(\underline{t}_1) > 0$, which contradicts (22). Now, if case b.) holds, then two scenarios can be found. On the one hand, if $\tau \geq \bar{t}_1 - l_u$ then by (19) one has that $u_2(t) - u_1(t) < 0, \forall t \in (\tau_0, \bar{t}_1 - l_u)$, which implies $\Delta y(\bar{t}_1) < 0$ by (24), leading to a contradiction with (21). On the other hand, to see what happens if $\tau < \bar{t}_1 - l_u$ let us rewrite (25) as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta y(\underline{t}_1) &= \int_{\tau_0}^{\bar{t}_1 - l_u} h_u(\underline{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \\ &\quad + \int_{\bar{t}_1 - l_u}^{\underline{t}_1} h_u(\underline{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \\ &\geq \epsilon \int_{\tau_0}^{\bar{t}_1 - l_u} h_u(\bar{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \\ &\quad + \int_{\bar{t}_1 - l_u}^{\underline{t}_1} h_u(\underline{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)[u_2(\theta) - u_1(\theta)] d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where $\epsilon = \min_{\theta \in [\tau_0, \bar{t}_1 - l_u]} h_u(\underline{t}_1 - \theta - l_u)/h_u(\bar{t}_1 - \theta - l_u) \geq 0$. From (24) and (21), the first integral term in (26) is greater than zero. The second term is strictly greater than zero, because $u_2(t) - u_1(t) > 0, \forall t > \bar{t}_1 - l_u$ by (20) in this scenario. Therefore, it follows from (26) that $\Delta y(\underline{t}_1) > 0$, which also contradicts (22). This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 1. *The best set of tuning parameters for the proposed controller is $\alpha \rightarrow 0^+, r = r_d, k = k^\dagger(\alpha, r_d)$, for which the following holds*

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\tau_0}^{\tau_0 + \epsilon} u(t, \alpha, r, k^\dagger) dt = B^*(\tau_0) \quad (27)$$

Proof. The best set of parameters is an immediate consequence of Theorem 2, given the parameter constraints $r \geq r_d$ and $\alpha > 0$ stated in Theorem 1. Setting $r = r_d, k = k^\dagger(\alpha, r_d), T = \tau_0 + \epsilon$ in (9) with $\epsilon > 0$ and letting $\alpha \rightarrow 0^+$ yields $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\tau_0}^{\tau_0 + \epsilon} u(t, \alpha, r, k^\dagger) dt = M \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} k^\dagger(\alpha, r_d)$, and the equality $M \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} k^\dagger(\alpha, r_d) = B^*(\tau_0)$ follows from (16) and (17), which completes the proof. \square

Remark 5 (Controller sub-optimality). *The implication of (27) is that, as a limit case, the proposed controller leads to an optimally-sized bolus, delivered at time τ_0 . As described in Remark 4, this is the best control policy that can be generated by feedback. Therefore, it has been shown that the proposed strategy approaches the optimal closed-loop performance as a limit case (see Fig. 3 for an illustration). It should be remarked that these results hold under Assumption 1 and thus performance is unavoidable affected by model uncertainties.*

Remark 6 (Limitations). *The parameter $\alpha > 0$ cannot be made arbitrarily small in practice but it has to be adjusted to reach a tradeoff between performance and robustness. The sampling period is also a limitation because the fast dynamics in the control action when $\alpha \rightarrow 0^+$ needs also fast update rates to be implemented, which are limited by the sensor and pump capabilities. Note that choosing large values of α will not jeopardize the closed-loop stability.*

Remark 7 (Relaxing Assumption 2). *In practice, the control input is allowed to take negative values up to $-u_b$, which would result in an insulin pump shutdown. Assumption 2 can be relaxed by using a different filter with a real zero $\tilde{Q}(s) \triangleq Q(s)(\beta s + 1)$ with $Q(s)$ defined in (5), subject to $\beta > \alpha$ and $r \geq r_d + 1$. Let $\tilde{u}(t, \alpha, \beta, r, k)$ be the new control signal resulting from applying the filter $\tilde{Q}(s)$. From (4), the control signal is affine with respect to the Q -filter and thus $\tilde{u}(s) = (\beta s + 1)u(s)$. Then, by the Laplace differentiation property, one has that $\tilde{u}(t) = \beta \dot{u}(t) + u(t)$, with $u(t)$ previously defined in (6). Some simple calculations lead to*

$$\tilde{u}(t, \alpha, \beta, r, k) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < \tau_0 \\ \frac{kM}{\alpha^{r+1}(r-1)!} [\alpha\beta(r-1) + (\alpha-\beta)(t-\tau_0)] (t-\tau_0)^{r-2} e^{-\frac{t-\tau_0}{\alpha}}, & t \geq \tau_0 \end{cases}$$

The absolute minimum of $\tilde{u}(t)$ is negative and it occurs at

$$\check{t} \triangleq \tau_0 + \frac{\alpha}{2(\beta-\alpha)} \left[(2\beta-\alpha)\rho + \sqrt{\rho} \sqrt{\alpha^2\rho - 4\alpha\beta + 4\beta^2} \right]$$

with $\rho = r - 1$, which can be seen by analyzing its critical points, that is, the solutions to $\dot{\tilde{u}}(t) = 0$ (this procedure, simple but lengthy, is omitted). Therefore, the constraint $\tilde{u}(t, \alpha, \beta, r, k) \geq -u_b, \forall t \geq 0$ will hold for any $\alpha < \beta \leq \bar{\beta}$ where $\bar{\beta}$ is the solution to $\tilde{u}(\check{t}, \alpha, \bar{\beta}, r, k) = -u_b$.

Remark 8 (Implementation). *The implementation of the proposed strategy is extremely simple. The controller (3) is obtained as described in Section 2, which is then discretized at the appropriate sampling period (typically 5 min in order to match current CGM and insulin pump capabilities). The resulting difference equation can be easily implemented in any embedded device with limited computational resources.*

Figure 2: CGM variation normalized by meal CHO content: postprandial responses segmented from the data set (dotted blue), median value (solid blue) and response of the identified model (red)

4. Numerical example

In this section, a linear model is identified from in-silico data generated with an extended version of the UVa/Padova metabolic simulator. The identification procedure is first explained. Then, the theoretical results are illustrated with closed-loop simulations under nominal conditions. Finally, the feasibility of this approach in the presence of uncertainties is illustrated in-silico.

4.1. Patient identification

An extended version of the S2013 UVa/Padova simulator [36], incorporating sinusoidal variation of insulin sensitivity [37] and time-varying changes in pharmacokinetic parameters up to 30% [15], was used to generate a data set for identification. It should be remarked that the simulator implements measurement error and noise models to mimic an actual CGM device [38]. A conventional open-loop therapy was implemented for one of the virtual patients of the simulator, in a 14-day scenario generated with randomness in the meal size, intake time and carbohydrate counting errors. The postprandial responses (three per day) are shown in Fig. 2, which were segmented from the CGM data set. The CGM variations with respect to the basal value of this patient, $G_b = 123.4$ mg/dL, divided by the size of the corresponding meal are displayed (dotted blue) along with the median value (solid blue), denoted by $y_{cgm}^M(t)$. Using the linear model (1)-(2) with $t_0 = 0$, and modeling the open-loop conventional therapy by $u(t) = kd(t)$, the following expression for the model-based meal-normalized postprandial response is

K_u	K_d	τ_u	τ_d	τ_g	l_u, l_d	r_u, r_d
250	60	60	20	420	15	3

Table 1: Identified model parameters

α	$k^*(\alpha, r_d)$	$\max_t y(t)$
6	221	84
4	224	81
2	226	77
----- $\bar{B}^*(\bar{\tau}_0)$		----- 73

Table 2: Control parameters and performance indices

obtained

$$y_{model}^M(s) \triangleq \frac{y(s)}{M} = \left(\frac{K_d}{(\tau_d s + 1)^2} - k \frac{K_u}{(\tau_u s + 1)^2} \right) \frac{e^{-15s}}{\tau_g s + 1} \quad (28)$$

where the parameters $r_d = r_u = 3$ and $l_d = l_u = 15$ min were fixed based on the literature [39, 19]. Furthermore, the parameter constraints $\tau_{u_1} = \tau_{u_2} \triangleq \tau_u$, $\tau_{u_1} = \tau_{u_2} \triangleq \tau_u$ and $\tau_{u_3} = \tau_{d_3} \triangleq \tau_g$ were introduced based on physiological and practical identifiability considerations. These constraints imply that: i.) the meal and insulin absorption processes are represented by two-compartment models with time constants τ_d and τ_u , respectively; ii.) they have an additive effect on the glucose metabolism process, represented by a first-order model with time constant τ_g . These constraints help to avoid identifiability issues and to obtain a model that is physiologically meaningful [40]. These parameters were identified by minimizing the root mean squared error (RMSE) between the median meal-normalized CGM data $y_{cgm}^M(t)$ and the model-based meal-normalized response $y_{model}^M(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{y_{model}^M(s)\}(t)$, computed from (28). The whole parameter space was partitioned and an exhaustive search was performed. This procedure led to the parameters $K_u = 250$ (mg/dL)/(pmol/kg/min), $K_d = 60$ (mg/dL)/(mg/kg/min), $\tau_u = 60$ min, $\tau_d = 20$ min and $\tau_g = 420$ min, which are summarized in Table 1. An RMSE between the median CGM data (blue) and the fitted model (red) in Fig. 2 of 0.04 (mg/dL)/(g CHO) was obtained. Please note that the identification is performed upon data that is normalized by the meal carbohydrate content (CHO), which means that for a typical medium-size meal (70 g CHO) [41], the fitted model yields a 2.8 mg/dL RMSE. It should be remarked that this a batch offline identification procedure that could be applied in practice based on CGM, meal intakes and insulin infusion data collected from a diabetic patient.

4.2. Nominal simulations

The theoretical results are first illustrated in the nominal case using the linear model identified above. The proposed controller is implemented through (3) and (5) with $r = r_d = 3$, which was shown to be the optimal value in Corollary 1. The controller is discretized with a sampling period of 5 min, which is

the update rate provided by current CGM devices. Simulations were run considering a medium-size meal with a CHO content of 70 g delivered at $t_0 = 60$ min. Different values of the tuning parameter $\alpha > 0$ were tested, while the optimal value $k = k^\dagger(\alpha, r_d)$ was set for each case. The latter was computed as explained in Lemma 2 to achieve a prescribed minimum glucose drop of $y^{min} = -10$ mg/dL below the basal value.

The results are shown in Fig. 3, where one can see that smaller values of α in the proposed controller (solid lines) result in a smaller blood glucose peak while keeping the minimum at the specified threshold (dashed green). For illustration purposes, the following open-loop (that is, with intervention of the patient) control policies are represented:

- $B^*(\tau_u^*)$ (dotted black): this is the optimal open-loop policy. It is found by trial-and-error that $\tau_u^* = t_0 - 25$ min, that is, the optimal bolus must be delivered 25 min before mealtime. Not only it is impossible to generate this policy by feedback, but also it is never used in practice because it implies serious risks. If the meal disturbance was delayed for any reason (likely to happen eating at restaurant, for example), the patient would suffer from severe hypoglycemia. Furthermore, errors in carbohydrate counting or unexpected changes in the patient insulin sensitivity may also result in hypoglycemia.
- $B^*(t_0)$ (dash-dotted black): this open-loop policy is a common practice, in which the diabetic patient delivers a bolus at mealtime. Unfortunately, it is impossible to generate this control policy using only feedback from blood glucose measurements, as it has been already discussed in Remarks 3 and 4.
- $B^*(\tau_0)$ (dashed black): As pointed out in Remark 4, this open-loop policy yields best performance that can be achieved by feedback. Indeed, the results show (see also Table 2) how the proposed controller (solid lines) approach this policy as α goes to zero, corroborating Corollary 1.

4.3. Robustness simulations

In order to illustrate the feasibility and robustness of the proposed controller, a 14-day closed-loop simulation is performed using the simulator described above in Section 4.1, which includes many sources of uncertainties. The proposed strategy is implemented with $k = 6000[\text{pmol}/\text{U}] \times \eta/\text{I2C}$, which could be also used in a clinical trial, as explained in Remark 1. The parameter $\text{I2C} = 22.4$ g/U is provided by the simulator and $\eta = 0.7$ is selected as a safety factor. For a better visualization of the intra-day and inter-day uncertainty, 24-hour simulations were run with 60 g, 70 g and 60 g meals for breakfast, lunch and dinner, respectively, and median values and interquartile ranges are shown in Fig. 4. For the

Figure 3: Nominal performance illustration with a linear system

sake of comparison, the meal detection based algorithm [25] was also implemented (black) along with the proposed strategy with $\alpha = 3$ (blue). It is observed that, although the meal detection algorithm leads to large impulses, these are delivered too late (some time is needed for the algorithm to ensure that a meal intake has occurred because false positives could be life-threatening). Consequently, the proposed strategy leads to better performance than [25], reducing the postprandial peaks by about 8%. Also, it should be pointed out that the proposed controller has only one parameter that is tuned with a clinical rule, while meal detection based controllers like [25] have many parameters that can only be tuned by trial-and-error through extensive simulations. Finally, as a benchmark comparison, the standard open-loop therapy $B^*(t_0)$, which requires the patient intervention at mealtime, is also illustrated (red). The open-loop therapy performs slightly better in terms of reduced postprandial peak. This is expected due to the closed-loop limitations already discussed (see Remarks 3 and 4). Nevertheless, the proposed controller has a clear effect in reducing CGM variability, resulting in a narrower interquartile range and smaller blood glucose drop during the postprandial period, thus reducing the risk of hypoglycemia. This is achieved in spite of all the uncertainties (model structure, non-linearity, random parameter variation and noise) and more importantly, without intervention of the patient.

Appendix A. Proof of Lemma 1

Let $X^* = \min_{t \geq \min\{\tau_0, l_u + \tau_u\}} \left(\frac{h_d(t - \tau_0) - y^{min}/M}{h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u)} \right) M$ and B^* the optimally-sized bolus in (15). First of all, some inequalities involving X^* will be derived. In what follows, in order to simplify notation, let us

Figure 4: Feasibility illustration using an extended version of the UVa/Padova simulator: median (solid) and interquartile values (shaded)

denote by $y_X(t)$ the postprandial response (13), subject to the prototype control input $u(t) = X\delta(t - \tau_u)$, which can be expressed as

$$y_X(t) = Mh_d(t - \tau_0) - Xh_u(t - l_u - \tau_u), \quad \forall t \geq t_{ini} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $t_{ini} = \min\{\tau_0, l_u + \tau_u\}$, meaning that $y_X(t) = 0, \forall t < t_{ini}$. From (A.1), if $\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_X(t) \geq y^{min}$ then $y_X(t) \geq y^{min}, \forall t \geq t_{ini}$. Hence, by definition of X^* and solving the inequality for X , yields

$$\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_X(t) \geq y^{min} \implies X \leq X^* \quad (\text{A.2})$$

On the other hand, $X^* \leq (Mh_d(t - \tau_0) - y^{min})/h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u), \forall t \geq t_{ini}$ by its own definition, and thus $-X^*h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u) \geq Mh_d(t - \tau_0) - y^{min}, \forall t \geq t_{ini}$. Using this bound into (A.1) evaluated for $X = X^*$, the following inequality can be obtained

$$\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{X^*}(t) \geq y^{min} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Also, it should be recalled that the optimal bolus size B^* in (15) is defined such that

$$\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{B^*}(t) = y^{min} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The rest of the proof follows by contradiction. Let us make the hypothesis that $B^* \neq X^*$. Since (A.4) holds, using (A.2) for $X = B^*$ yields $B^* \leq X^*$ and thus B^* cannot be strictly greater than X^* . Next, let us check that B^* cannot be strictly less than X^* either. If $B^* < X^*$, evaluating (A.1) for $X = \{B^*, X^*\}$ and subtracting them, it is obtained that $y_{B^*}(t) - y_{X^*}(t) = (X^* - B^*)h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u) \geq 0, \forall t \geq t_{ini}$, which follows from $B^* < X^*$ and the fact that $h_u(t - l_u - \tau_u)$ is positive for all t . Therefore, one has that $y_{B^*}(t) \geq y_{X^*}(t), \forall t \geq t_{ini}$, or, alternatively,

$$\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{B^*}(t) \geq \min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{X^*}(t) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Now, using (A.3)-(A.5), the following inequality is deduced

$$y^{min} \geq \min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{X^*}(t) \geq y^{min}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Therefore, $\min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{X^*}(t) = y^{min} = \min_{t \geq t_{ini}} y_{B^*}(t)$, leading to the conclusion that $B^* = X^*$, which is a contradiction, completing the proof.

Appendix B. Proof of Lemma 2

The proof is only drafted because it follows from the same arguments applied in the proof of Lemma 1. In this case, let us denote by $y_k(t)$ the closed-loop postprandial response computed from (1)-(2) and (8), which can be expressed as

$$y_k(t) = Mh_d(t - \tau_0) - k(\alpha, r)M(h_u * f)(t - l_u - \tau_0), \quad \forall t \geq \tau_0 \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $y_k(t) = 0, \forall t < \tau_0$ and $f(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{(\alpha s + 1)^{-r}\}(t)$. The rest of the proof, which is omitted, consists in showing that $\min_{t \geq \tau_0} y_k(t) = y^{min}$ if and only if $k(\alpha, r) = k^\dagger(\alpha, r)$, which follows by the same procedure as in Lemma 1, where k^\dagger and y_k play the role of B^* and y_X , respectively.

Appendix C. Proof of Lemma 3

Let us define $z(t) = u_1(t)/u_2(t) > 0, \forall t > \tau_0$, which can be expressed using (6) as

$$z(t) = \frac{k_1 \alpha_2^{r_2} (r_2 - 1)!}{k_2 \alpha_1^{r_1} (r_1 - 1)!} (t - \tau_0)^{r_1 - r_2} e^{-(t - \tau_0) \frac{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1}{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

for all $t > \tau_0$. Next, differentiating (C.1) and performing some simple manipulations yields

$$z'(t) = \frac{(t - \tau_0)(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) + (r_1 - r_2)\alpha_1\alpha_2}{(t - \tau_0)\alpha_1\alpha_2} z(t) < 0$$

for all $t > \tau_0$ and thus $z(t)$ is a strictly decreasing function in the domain (τ_0, ∞) . It is clear that at the right-end $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} z(t) = 0$, provided that $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2$. However, at the left-end, two scenarios are possible. On the one hand, if $r_1 \neq r_2$, then $\lim_{t \rightarrow \tau_0^+} z(t) = \infty$ and thus the range of $z(t)$ is $(0, \infty)$. Since $z(t)$ is continuous and strictly decreasing, there exists a unique $\tau > \tau_0$ such that $z(\tau) = 1$, which corresponds to case b.). Furthermore, (19)-(20) follow from the fact that $z(t) > 1, \forall t \in (\tau_0, \tau)$ and $z(t) < 1, \forall t > \tau$. On the other hand, if $r = r_1 = r_2$ then $\lim_{t \rightarrow \tau_0^+} z(t) = k_1/k_2(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)^r$ and thus the range in this case is $(0, k_1/k_2(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)^r)$. By the same reasoning, there exists $\tau > \tau_0$ such that $z(\tau) = 1$ if and only if $k_1/k_2(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)^r > 1$, leading also to the case b.). However, if $k_1/k_2(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)^r \leq 1$, that is, if $k_2 \geq k_1(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)^r \triangleq \kappa$, then case a.) follows.

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